

Total internal reflection from an amplifying or attenuating medium

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This Letter addresses the question of total internal reflection of a plane wave from an amplifying or attenuating medium. The Fresnel reflection coefficients are modified to take into account the effect of optical gain or loss in the low-index medium. If applied to the analysis of an asymmetric planar waveguide having gain or loss in the cladding region, the derived formulas allow us to reproduce the fractional overlap between the optical power flowing in the guided modes and the amplifying or attenuating medium, and to predict the resulting modal gain or loss.

Since its conception [1], there have been many reports on the investigation of optical amplification by means of total internal reflection from an amplifying low-index medium. This idea, which bears a few different names such as evanescent-field amplification, evanescent gain, amplified total internal reflection, and enhanced internal reflection, has been implemented experimentally by use of different structures and materials [2-6]. As for its theoretical understanding, however, a unanimous agreement on the mechanism for the phenomenon has yet to be established [7-10]. It has even been argued that a reflection coefficient exceeding unity is unfeasible [11].

The past theoretical works that support the existence of such evanescent gain essentially assume that the amplification by stimulated emission somehow occurs perpendicular to the interface between the high-index transparent medium and low-index gain medium [7-10]. This, however, presents a physical picture inconsistent with the textbook knowledge of stimulated transitions. Namely, the light intensity growth resulting from stimulated emission should be in the same direction as the Poynting vector of evanescent field, which is parallel, not perpendicular, to the boundary separating two media [12].

In the following, two things are done. First, we derive the Fresnel coefficients for total reflection from an amplifying or attenuating low-index medium. Then, as an example involving evanescent-field amplification or attenuation upon total reflection, we take up analyzing a planar waveguide having gain or loss in the cladding region. Thereby the derived expressions are shown to reproduce the fraction of power associated with the

evanescent part of the guided mode that overlaps the gain or loss medium, and the resulting modal amplification or attenuation factors.

We start with total internal reflection from a transparent low-index medium. For an infinite plane wave incident at an angle α on a plane boundary separating two transparent media having indices of refraction n_h and n_l ($n_h > n_l$), above the critical angle, we have the Fresnel reflection coefficients [13]:

$$r_s = \frac{n_h \cos \alpha - i \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}}{n_h \cos \alpha + i \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}} \quad (1a)$$

and

$$r_p = \frac{n_l \cos \alpha - i (n_h/n_l) \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}}{n_l \cos \alpha + i (n_h/n_l) \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}} \quad (1b)$$

for s - and p -polarized waves, respectively. Here the s -component means the electric field perpendicular to the plane of incidence, and the p -component the electric field parallel to the plane of incidence. For total internal reflection, there is a small amount of lateral shift of the reflected wave with respect to the incident wave, which is called the Goos-Hänchen shift (Fig. 1). The expressions found by Renard using the energy conservation law hold at any incident angle, not just in the vicinity of the critical angle [14]:

$$l_s = \frac{2 \cos \alpha \sin \alpha}{\cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha - (n_l/n_h)^2} d_l \quad (2a)$$

$$l_p = \frac{2 (n_l/n_h)^2 \cos \alpha \sin \alpha}{(n_l/n_h)^4 \cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha - (n_l/n_h)^2} d_l \quad (2b)$$

for s - and p -polarized waves, respectively. Here the penetration depth d_l , defined as the

distance from the boundary plane where the amplitude drops to $1/e$ of the value at the boundary, is written as

$$d_l = \frac{\lambda_0}{2\pi \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}}, \quad (3)$$

where λ_0 is the wavelength in vacuum.

According to [14] in which the above expressions are derived, a given point on the wavefront, upon its incidence, traverses a distance equal to the Goos-Hänchen shift, l_s or l_p , depending on the polarization, in Medium l , along the x direction near the boundary plane and then emerges into Medium h . In [14], the author also emphasizes that the evanescent wave is a traveling wave, not a standing one, contrary to the oft-stated notion in literature.

We shall now proceed to deal with total reflection from an amplifying or attenuating medium. The effect of gain or loss can be incorporated by means of a complex refractive index: $\hat{n}_l = n_l - i n_l'$ [12]. Here the imaginary part of the complex index is assumed to be sufficiently small so that the quantities such as the angle of refraction and penetration depth remain virtually unaffected by the presence of gain or loss.

Here we make an assumption that the transitions responsible for evanescent gain or loss in the low-index medium are induced by the traveling inhomogeneous plane waves and take place along the very optical path that produces the Goos-Hänchen shift. The amplitude of the refracted wave in the x direction evolves as the imaginary part of $\exp(-i k_0 \hat{n}_2 x)$:

$$r'_s = \exp(-k_0 n'_l l_s) \quad (4a)$$

for s -polarized waves and

$$r'_p = \exp(-k_0 n'_l l_p) \quad (4b)$$

for p -polarized waves. Here l_s and l_p are given by Eqs. (2a) and (2b), respectively.

Combining the conventional Fresnel reflection coefficients, Eqs. (1a) and (1b), responsible for phase shifts, and the expressions for the amplitude changes, Eqs. (4a) and (4b), we find the coefficients \hat{r}'_s and \hat{r}'_p for amplified or attenuated internal reflections:

$$\hat{r}'_s = r'_s r_s = \frac{n_h \cos \alpha - i \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}}{n_h \cos \alpha + i \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}} \exp(-k_0 n'_l l_s) \quad (5a)$$

and

$$\hat{r}'_p = r'_p r_p = \frac{n_h \cos \alpha - i (n_h/n_l) \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}}{n_h \cos \alpha + i (n_h/n_l) \sqrt{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2}} \exp(-k_0 n'_l l_p) \quad (5b)$$

We can see that, for $n'_l < 0$, reflection coefficients exceeding unity naturally come about. Note that the formulas Eqs. (5a) and (5b) have been developed without resorting to an unfamiliar physical picture in which the amplitude change occurs perpendicular to the direction of the Poynting vector in the evanescent region as in [7-10]. We might add that, in the classical theory of electrodynamics, the imaginary part of a complex refractive index can account for loss caused not only by absorption but also by scattering. As the imaginary part of the index n'_l tends towards zero, the derived expressions, Eqs. (5a) and (5b) reduce to the original Fresnel reflection coefficients.

To see if the expressions formulated above make any physical sense at all in the context of a situation involving total internal reflection, we take up as an example a planar waveguide having gain or loss in the cladding region.

Here an asymmetrical planar waveguide is assumed (Fig. 2), whose core region of thickness D and index of n_h is sandwiched by the amplifying or attenuating low-index cladding region of index $\hat{n}_l = n_l - i n_l'$, and transparent substrate of index n_s . In a planar waveguide, a guided mode is viewed as a superposition of two plane waves, one incident and the other one reflected. We imagine a guided mode, either TE or TM, with an incident angle of α . While traversing a distance L in the x direction and experiencing successive reflections at the both sides of the core, the guided mode, at each total reflection at the core-cladding boundary, suffers a Goos-Hänchen shift accompanied by a small amount of gain or loss. If we ignore the phase change, the incremental intensity change accumulated by the guided TE mode through multiple reflections is written as

$$\begin{aligned} G_s &= [r_s'^2]^{N_s} \\ &= \exp(-2k_0 n_l' l_s N_s L / \Delta L_s), \end{aligned} \quad (6a)$$

where the total number of reflections at the cladding-core boundary is given by $N_s = L / \Delta L_s$. Here ΔL_s is the distance between two successive reflections at the core-cladding interface: $\Delta L_s = 2(d_l + T + d_s) \tan \alpha$. The penetration depths in the cladding and substrate regions, d_l and d_s are given by Eq. (3) and

$$d_s = \frac{\lambda_0}{2\pi\sqrt{n_h^2\sin^2\alpha - n_s^2}}, \quad (7)$$

respectively.

Introducing a quantity $\eta_s = l_s/\Delta L_s$, we rewrite Eq. (6a) as

$$G_s = \exp(-2\eta_s k_0 n_l' L). \quad (8a)$$

Similarly, for TM modes, we have

$$\begin{aligned} G_p &= [r_p r^2]^{Np} \\ &= \exp(-2k_0 n_l' l_p N_p L / \Delta l_p), \end{aligned} \quad (6b)$$

from which we get

$$G_p = \exp(-2\eta_p k_0 n_l' L), \quad (8b)$$

where $\eta_p = l_p/\Delta L_p$. In Eqs. (6a) and (6b), $2k_0 n_l'$ is the material gain coefficient, and the quantities η_s and η_p , are viewed as some proportionality constants.

With Eq. (2a) and $\Delta L_s = 2(d_l + T + d_s) \tan \alpha$, the quantity, $\eta_s = l_s/\Delta L_s$, becomes

$$\eta_s = \frac{n_l^2 \cos^2 \alpha}{(T + d_l + d_s)(n_h^2 - n_s^2)} d_l. \quad (9a)$$

For TM modes, using Eq. (2b) and $\Delta L_p = (d_l' + T + d_s') \tan \alpha$, we carry out similar rearrangements, which require a little more patience, to get

$$\eta_p = \frac{n_l^2 \cos^2 \alpha}{(T + d_l' + d_s')(n_h^2 - n_s^2)} d_l', \quad (9b)$$

where d_l' and d_s' are given by the following

$$d'_l = \frac{n_l^2}{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_l^2 \cos^2 \alpha} d_l \quad (10)$$

and

$$d'_s = \frac{n_s^2}{n_h^2 \sin^2 \alpha - n_s^2 \cos^2 \alpha} d_s \quad (11)$$

Equations (9a) and (9b) are the expressions for the fractions of optical power flowing in the evanescent TE and TM fields [15]. Starting with an assumption that, at each total reflection, the amplitude undergoes a change by a factor of $\exp(-k_0 n_l' l_s)$ or $\exp(-k_0 n_l' l_p)$, we have arrived at the proportionality constants η_s and η_p , which now turn out to be the cross-sectional overlap between the guided mode and the amplifying or attenuating cladding. Based on η_s and η_p , the modal gain or loss can be calculated as Eqs. (8a) and (8b) [16].

In summary, a modification to the Fresnel coefficients has been established for total internal reflection from an amplifying or attenuating low-index medium. The reflection coefficients describe either evanescent gain or loss, depending on the sign of the imaginary part of the complex refractive index. Furthermore, applying the derived formulas to the guided mode analysis has led us to the expected modal gain or loss of an asymmetric planar waveguide having an amplifying or attenuating cladding.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the Goos-Hänchen shift. The symbol l corresponds to either l_s or l_p in the main body of the text.

Fig. 2 Schematic trajectory of a guided mode in the planar waveguide with the top cladding layer exhibiting gain or loss ($\hat{n}_l = n_l - i n_l'$) and the transparent substrate (n_s). The symbol ΔL represents either ΔL_s or ΔL_p in the main text. The penetration depths d_l and d_s should read d_l' and d_s' , respectively, for the TM modes.

Fig. 1 T. Kobayashi

Fig. 2 T. Kobayashi